

AUTOMATIC SERVING-FOCUSED BENCHMARKING OF MODELS

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AUTHOR(S):

Tomasz Wojnar

CERN, IT-CD-PI

SUPERVISOR(S):

Raulian-Ionut Chiorescu

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Objective: To create an automated system for benchmarking machine learning models, focusing on their performance in production serving environments.

Key Tasks:

- **Automate Performance Evaluation:** Benchmark any registered model.
- **Measure User-Side Performance:** Monitor latency and resource consumption (CPU/RAM) to ensure acceptable thresholds.
- **Identify Hotspots:** Use profiling tools to pinpoint performance bottlenecks within models (e.g., via heatmaps).
- **Benchmark Diverse Runtimes:** Evaluate performance across various serving platforms (e.g., Triton, TFServing, TorchServe, MLflow ModelServer, ONNX).

Outcomes: This project will ensure quality of service for production models and enhance the debugging experience for performance issues.

ABSTRACT

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The increasing use of machine learning models in production environments requires a systematic and standardized approach to evaluating their performance. Due to significant variations in architecture, size, precision and underlying framework, performance prediction and debugging are complex tasks. This project introduces the ML Inference Benchmark Tool: an automated system designed to benchmark registered models from the user’s perspective. The tool provides a thorough analysis of important performance indicators, such as latency percentiles, throughput and resource consumption (CPU, GPU and RAM). Supporting multiple serving runtimes and frameworks, including PyTorch, TensorFlow, and ONNX, it uses deep profiling capabilities to identify computational hotspots at the operator level. Integrating with Kubeflow pipelines and using TensorBoard for rich visualization automates the evaluation process, ensures quality of service for production-grade models, and significantly improves the user experience when diagnosing performance-related issues.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	4
1.1	Machine Learning in Next Generation Triggers	4
1.2	The Need for Standardized Model Benchmarking	4
1.3	Project Goals and Objectives	5
2	BENCHMARKING METHODOLOGY	5
2.1	Supported Backends and Frameworks	5
2.2	Core Performance Metrics	5
2.3	Operator-Level Profiling	6
2.4	Data Format and Configuration	7
3	SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE	8
3.1	Core Components	8
3.2	External Integrations	9
4	TENSORBOARD VISUALIZATIONS	9
5	CONCLUSION AND FEATURE WORK	10
5.1	Summary of Achievements	10
5.2	Future Enhancements	10

1 INTRODUCTION

The deployment of machine learning models in production systems has become standard practice across industries. However, moving a model from a research environment to a live production-grade service introduces a new set of challenges centered on performance, reliability, and resource efficiency. A model that is highly accurate but fails to meet latency requirements or consumes excessive resources is impractical for real-world applications. In this report, we introduce a comprehensive tool designed to automate the performance benchmarking of machine learning (ML) models and address these critical challenges.

1.1 Machine Learning in Next Generation Triggers

In high-energy physics experiments such as those conducted at CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC), vast amounts of data are generated at an enormous rate - billions of collisions per second. It is not possible to store and process all these raw data, so real-time trigger systems are used to filter and select only a tiny fraction of 'interesting' events for further analysis.

The upcoming High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) will present even greater challenges, with significantly higher data rates and more complex events [5]. Machine learning is therefore becoming essential for next-generation trigger systems [4, 6, 1].

Machine learning is pivotal for these next-generation trigger systems for the following reasons:

- **Ultra-low-latency decisions:** ML models, which are often deployed on specialized hardware such as FPGAs and GPUs, enable microsecond-level decisions that are critical for the initial trigger stages [3].
- **Enhanced event selection:** ML algorithms provide superior precision in classifying events and identifying complex physics signatures, thereby improving the signal-to-noise ratio [3].
- **Anomaly detection:** A critical application is the use of ML for anomaly detection, which involves identifying unexpected patterns and is essential for the discovery of new physics beyond the Standard Model [2].

The Next Generation Triggers project is a five-year initiative that was launched in January 2024. It explicitly focuses on leveraging advanced AI and computing to address these challenges and maximize the scientific potential of the HL-LHC [1]. Due to strict latency and throughput requirements, it is essential to rigorously and automatically benchmark these ML models to ensure quality of service and facilitate groundbreaking scientific discoveries at the HL-LHC.

1.2 The Need for Standardized Model Benchmarking

Deploying ML models in production requires more than just accuracy; it demands guaranteed performance. Ad hoc testing is insufficient for ensuring quality of service. Key challenges include the diversity of ML frameworks, identifying performance bottlenecks, analysing complex metrics beyond simple averages and ensuring reproducible results. A dedicated and standardised benchmarking tool is essential to address these challenges.

1.3 Project Goals and Objectives

The primary goal of this project was to develop an automated system for evaluating the performance of any registered model, with a focus on metrics relevant to production serving. The key objectives were:

- **Develop a multi-framework tool** capable of benchmarking models from PyTorch, TensorFlow, and ONNX Runtime.
- **Implement comprehensive metric collection** for latency, throughput, and system resource utilization.
- **Integrate deep profiling tools** to generate operator-level performance data and identify computational hotspots.
- **Provide rich visualizations** of results using TensorBoard for intuitive analysis.
- **Automate the benchmarking process** by creating reusable Kubeflow pipeline components.

2 BENCHMARKING METHODOLOGY

An effective evaluation of the performance of machine learning models in a production context demands a systematic and robust methodology. The ML Inference Benchmark Tool takes a comprehensive approach, providing reliable, actionable insights. This includes an initial warm-up phase to ensure system stability and proper resource allocation, followed by the precise measurement of key performance indicators and detailed operator-level profiling. The tool also offers flexible configuration options.

2.1 Supported Backends and Frameworks

The tool supports benchmarking across the most popular machine learning frameworks, ensuring broad applicability:

- **PyTorch** (.pt, .pth), Input (PyTorch tensors)
- **ONNX Runtime** (.onnx), Input (NumPy arrays)
- **TensorFlow** (.keras, SavedModel), Input (TensorFlow tensors)

This broad support enables direct comparisons to be made between the performance of models across different frameworks and optimised runtimes. This provides valuable insights for deployment decisions:

2.2 Core Performance Metrics

Following the warm-up phase, a comprehensive suite of metrics is collected to understand the model's behaviour under realistic conditions. These metrics provide a comprehensive overview of performance, which is essential for optimising models for production environments:

- **Latency** This quantifies the time taken for a single inference request to be processed from start to finish. Critical for real-time applications where quick responses are important, such as autonomous systems or real-time data filtering in trigger systems.
- **Throughput** Measures the total number of inference requests or data samples that the system can process in a given time period (e.g. per second). Essential for understanding the model's processing capacity and scalability. High throughput indicates the efficient utilisation of hardware, which is vital for handling large volumes of data or concurrent requests in high-demand scenarios.
- **Resource Utilisation** Tracks the consumption of system resources (e.g. CPU, GPU and memory) during the inference process. Crucial for cost efficiency and identifying potential hardware bottlenecks. Monitoring resource usage helps to select the right infrastructure, optimise deployment configurations and ensure that the model runs efficiently without over- or under-provisioning resources.

2.3 Operator-Level Profiling

Beyond external metrics such as latency and throughput, it is important to understand the internal execution dynamics of a model in order to optimise it effectively. In machine learning, profiling involves instrumenting the model's execution to gather detailed timing and resource consumption data at a granular level, often down to individual operations or layers. This process provides a detailed view of where computational time is being spent, thereby pinpointing bottlenecks that might not be evident from high-level metrics alone. By identifying these 'hotspots', developers can focus their optimisation efforts on the areas that will have the greatest impact, leading to significant performance gains.

To pinpoint performance bottlenecks effectively, the tool uses operation-level profiling tools provided by backends and frameworks. This process captures execution times for individual operations within the model graph. The granular data obtained from operator profiling enables developers to:

- Identify specific computationally intensive operations.
- Evaluate the performance impact of different model architectures or optimisation techniques on individual operators.
- Direct targeted optimisation efforts, such as kernel fusion, precision reduction or the development of custom operators.

2.4 Data Format and Configuration

The input data for our benchmarking follows the [KServe](#) standard for inference requests, ensuring a consistent and widely compatible format. This standardisation simplifies integration with various serving runtimes and enables clear communication of input tensor properties. A KServe JSON payload for a single input tensor typically looks like this:

```
{
  "inputs": [
    {
      "name": "input_tensor",
      "shape": [-1, 3, 224, 224],
      "datatype": "FP32",
      "data": [[[[[0.1, 0.2, ...]]]]]
    }
  ]
}
```

Listing 1: Example KServe Inference Request Payload.

In addition to data formatting, [Hydra](#) manages the tool's execution parameters. This powerful configuration framework enables flexible overriding of parameters such as batch size, the device to be used (CPU or CUDA) and iteration counts for different measurement phases, either directly from the command line or via structured configuration files. This flexibility is essential for adapting benchmarks to different models, hardware and performance objectives. Below is an example of a `config.yaml` file, which sets default parameters for a benchmark run:

```
logging_level: INFO
profiler:
  _target_: srcprofilers.tensorflow.TensorFlowProfiler
model_path: data/example_model.keras
payload_path: data/example_payload.json
config:
  warmup_iters: 10
  op_iters: 10
  latency_iters: 100
  throughput_seconds: 5
  monitor_intervals: 0.1
  batch_size: null
data_logger:
  _target_: src.tensorboard_logger.TensorboardLogger
  logdir: logs/tf
input_adapter:
  _target_: src.input_adapters.tensorflow.TensorFlowAdapter
device: cpu
```

Listing 2: Example Configuration File.

3 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The ML Inference Benchmark Tool has a modular, extensible architecture designed to support diverse ML frameworks, comprehensive metric collection, and easy integration into MLOps workflows. Its core design principles focus on flexibility, reusability, and clarity, enabling easy expansion to new frameworks or profiling techniques.

The sequence Fig. 1 illustrates the typical flow of interactions when running a benchmark.

Figure 1: UML Sequence Diagram of the ML Inference Benchmark Tool’s Execution Flow.

3.1 Core Components

The `src/` directory structure reflects the logical separation of concerns within the tool:

- **Profilers (`src/profilers`):** This is the heart of the benchmarking system.
 - `base.py`: Defines an abstract base profiler, establishing a common interface for all framework-specific profilers. This ensures consistency in how benchmarks are initiated, metrics are collected, and results are processed, regardless of the underlying ML framework.
 - `torch.py`, `onnx.py`, `tensorflow.py`: These modules implement the concrete profiling logic for PyTorch, ONNX Runtime, and TensorFlow respectively. They handle the specific nuances of loading models, preparing inputs, executing inference, and utilizing framework-native profiling tools (e.g., PyTorch profiler, TensorFlow profiler) for operator-level insights.
- **Input Adapters (`src/input_adapters/`):** Responsible for converting incoming benchmark data, which adheres to the KServe JSON format, into the specific tensor or array formats required by each ML framework (e.g., PyTorch Tensors, NumPy arrays, TensorFlow Tensors). This layer provides a standardised external API while accommodating the requirements of the internal frameworks.
- **Hydra Config (`src/config/`):** Leverages [Hydra](#) for robust and flexible configuration management. Users can easily define and override benchmark parameters (e.g. batch size, device and iteration counts) via command-line arguments or structured configuration files. This promotes reproducibility and ease of experimentation.

- **Resource Monitor** (`src/resource_monitor.py`): A dedicated component utilizing libraries like `psutil` and `pynvml` to actively track system-level resource usage (CPU, GPU, memory) throughout the inference process. It runs in parallel with inference to provide real-time resource footprint data.
- **TensorBoard Logger** (`src/tensorboard_logger.py`): Responsible for formatting and writing all collected performance metrics, resource utilization time series, and operator profiling traces in TensorBoard-compatible log directories. This enables a rich, interactive visualization of benchmark results.

3.2 External Integrations

- **TensorBoard Integration:** The tool logs the results directly to TensorBoard compatible directories. This gives users a powerful and familiar way to visualize and compare benchmark results, including interactive plots of latency distributions, throughput tables, resource usage time series, and detailed operator profiling traces. Users can then launch TensorBoard with the command `-logdir logs/` to view these results.
- **Kubeflow Pipeline Support:** The tool is designed with MLOps automation in mind. It includes ready-to-use Kubeflow pipeline components, enabling the entire benchmarking process to be integrated into a broader ML workflow. This enables automatic and reproducible performance validation whenever a new model version is registered or a new deployment environment is configured.

4 TENSORBOARD VISUALIZATIONS

This section illustrates the practical application and rich insights of the ML Inference Benchmark Tool by walking through a typical benchmarking scenario for a PyTorch model and highlighting the resulting TensorBoard visualizations.

The inference performance of a PyTorch ResNet-18 model on a CPU is evaluated by executing the following command:

```
run_benchmark \
  profiler=torch \
  profiler.device=cpu \
  profiler.model_path=data/example_model.pt \
  profiler.payload_path=data/example_payload.json \
  profiler.data_logger.logdir=logs/torch \
  profiler.config.throughput_seconds=5
```

Upon execution, the tool will perform the warm-up, latency, throughput, and operator profiling phases as described in Section 2, generating a comprehensive set of performance data. These results, which include configuration, key metrics, resource utilization, and operator-level details, can be explored in TensorBoard, as shown in Figs. 2, 3, and 4.

5 CONCLUSION AND FEATURE WORK

5.1 Summary of Achievements

The ML Inference Benchmark Tool provides a comprehensive, automated, and serving-focused solution for evaluating the performance of machine learning models. The project's key achievements include:

- **Multi-framework support:** Seamless benchmarking across PyTorch, ONNX Runtime, and TensorFlow.
- **Comprehensive metrics:** Collection of latency (including percentiles), throughput and real-time resource utilization (CPU, GPU and memory).
- **Deep profiling:** Operator-level insights to pinpoint computational bottlenecks.
- **Rich visualization:** Interactive results presented via TensorBoard.
- **Automated workflows:** Ready-to-use Kubeflow pipeline components for CI/CD integration.

This tool ensures the quality of service for production-grade models, improves performance debugging, and supports the reliable deployment of critical machine learning (ML) applications, particularly in high-demand fields such as the Next Generation Trigger project.

5.2 Future Enhancements

Although highly capable, the tool can be further enhanced:

- **Expanded Serving Runtime Support:** Direct benchmarking of various dedicated serving runtimes (e.g., Triton).
- **Distributed Inference Support:** Benchmarking for models deployed across multiple nodes or devices.
- **Precision Benchmarking:** Specific functionalities to evaluate performance trade-offs for different numerical precisions (e.g., FP32, FP16 and INT8).

(a) Benchmark Configuration Summary

(b) Latency and Throughput Metrics Summary

Figure 2: Illustrative TensorBoard visualizations from the **Text** view. (a) details the executed configuration parameters, while (b) presents a summary of key performance metrics including latency and throughput summaries.

Figure 3: Illustrative TensorBoard visualizations from the **Scalars** view, showing detailed resource usage during a benchmark run.

Operator View

All operators Top operators to show 10

Host Self Time (us)

- aten::mkldnn_convolution
- aten::native_batch_norm
- aten::max_pool2d_with_indices
- aten::add_
- aten::empty
- aten::clamp_min_
- aten::_convolution
- aten::_batch_norm_impl_index
- aten::convolution
- aten::addmm

Host Total Time (us)

- aten::conv2d
- aten::convolution
- aten::_convolution
- aten::mkldnn_convolution
- aten::batch_norm
- aten::_batch_norm_impl_index
- aten::native_batch_norm
- aten::max_pool2d
- aten::max_pool2d_with_indices
- aten::add_

Group By
Operator ▾

Search by Name

Name	Calls	Host Self Duration (us)	Host Total Duration (us)	Tensor Cores Eligible	Tensor Cores Self(%)	Tensor Cores Total(%)	
aten::mkldnn_convolution	200	523139	529291	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::native_batch_norm	200	36586	41093	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::max_pool2d_with_indices	10	26191	26191	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::add_	280	8220	8220	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::empty	2000	7654	7654	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::clamp_min_	170	5215	5215	No	0	0	View CallStack
aten::_convolution	200	3870	533161	Yes	0	0	View CallStack
aten::_batch_norm_impl_index	200	2780	44466	No	0	0	View CallStack

Figure 4: Illustrative TensorBoard visualizations from the **Profiler** view, specifically the Operator View, which breaks down execution time by individual model operations.

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